

1 Erap2 silencing by mutation of the NOD2 leucine-rich region.

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8 Antigen presentation was implicated by selective control of ERAP2 based on location of NOD2 mutation.

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10 Erap2 was not significantly affected by presence of single L1007P variants. The data demonstrate specific
11 dysregulation of the antigen presentation pathway by homozygous NOD2 variation (SNP13, L1007fsinsC,
12 L1007P_) that confers more significant risk of IBD than the other variants.

13 Citations

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